

Digital transformation in the Moroccan public sector: Literature review, state of the art and perspectives.

La Transformation Digitale au Secteur Public Marocain: Revue de littérature, état des lieux et perspectives.

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Abstract:

Digital transformation will necessarily have the same significant impact and technical/technological contribution requirements in the public or private sector, yet it is presented in different ways in both sectors. As far as the public sector is concerned, it is rare to find a public administration that attempts to seize this advantage, for several reasons. However, Moroccan public organizations seek to provide better services to citizens/users and their satisfaction, while focusing on their sustainable efficiency.

This article aims to establish a synthesis of the literature review and a state of the art to give a set of theoretical contributions and to better identify and understand the problem of Digital Transformation in the Moroccan public sector.

Keywords: Digital Transformation; public service; governance; E-Government; Morocco.

Résumé:

La transformation digitale aura forcément le même impact significatif et les conditions de contribution technique/technologique dans le secteur public ou du secteur privé, pourtant il est présenté de différentes manières dans les deux secteurs. En ce qui concerne le public, rarement qu'on trouve une administration publique qui tente de saisir cet avantage, pour plusieurs raisons, Cependant, les organisations publiques marocaines cherchent à fournir de meilleurs services aux citoyens / utilisateurs / usagers et leurs satisfaction, tout en mettant l'accent sur leur efficacité durable.

Cet article vise à établir une synthèse de la revue la littérature et un état des lieux pour objectif de donner un ensemble des apports théoriques et de mieux cerner et comprendre le problème de la Transformation digitale au secteur public marocain.

Mots Clés : Transformation digitale ; service public ; gouvernance ; E-Gouvernement; Maroc.

Introduction:

The 21st century can be considered as the era of the information revolution with regard to the prodigious development of information and communication technologies (ICT) which are now strategically located at the crossroads of all areas of human activity that they have invaded and at the same time transformed. Consequently, the invasion of almost all human activities by ICT now poses specific problems referring to the particularities of functions where tasks are not very formalized. The final objective of computerization is to bring a decisive help in the execution of the tasks through the inter connectivity and the interactivity between the man and the technological or computer tool.

This very important revolution concerns the circulation of information. Thanks to the Internet, the behavior of people within organizations is profoundly transformed. According to Isaac H.336, ICTs allow companies and administrations to enter the era of digitalization and to transform themselves into electronic administrations and digital companies. A United Nations study shows that these transformations are in continuous and progressive progress worldwide. For developed countries, e-government is seen as an efficiency tool, while for developing countries it represents an opportunity to reform and streamline government operations. Since the early 2000s, public administrations have been committed to simplifying their procedures and processes and improving the relationship with their users. Overall, we believe that the contributions of digitization technologies are important because they allow to be both up to date in the tasks to be accomplished and fast in the use and dissemination of information, between all parties. Moreover, digitalization technologies offer important advantages that can modify the organizational and managerial choices of public sector companies. These changes in choices are made in a context that aims to improve the administrative procedures carried out by public sector companies in an effective and efficient way, in order to quickly produce a quality final product and improve the degree of citizenship (Bressolles et al. 2014).

This being the case, organizations including those in the public sector are required to adapt to the changes brought by new ICTs in order to support their business objectives (Transparency, interoperability and citizen satisfaction). This is where digital transformation in the public sector comes in. It involves redeploying new ways of working with different stakeholders, creating new service delivery frameworks and new relational forms (Al-Hujran et al., 2015; European Commission & Directorate- General for Research and Innovation, 2013).

These same public sector companies need to keep up with technological developments by opting for digitalization, which would facilitate the establishment of a structured organizational platform (Babinet, 2016).

The use of ICT in the public sector helps to increase the level of efficiency of services and transparency, improving accountability in the procedures and management of public administration (Gupta et al. 2008).

The important role of ICT in modernizing the internal functioning of public organizations and public services. Thus, ICT accelerates and strengthens the decision-making mechanism for public policies, allows for effective decision support, better flow of information, mainly in aggregated form, and accurate and rapid evaluation of the results of the measures implemented. Similarly, electronic administration, or "e-administration", is a good response to the problem of user satisfaction.

Given the scarcity of scientific publications that study the impact of digital transformation in the public sector, our research aims to provide a theoretical reading of the digital situation in Morocco, based on documentary analysis of monitoring reports of reforms and projects at local level and secondary data from the Moroccan public sector. So no empirical work has been done in this regard.

We present a literature review on the topic of digital transformation in this research paper. Then we address the following question: What impact of digital transformation on the public sector in Morocco? We attempt to map the digitalization process in the Kingdom's public organizations by focusing on the particularity, objectives and impacts of this major investment. To do this, this paper is devoted to providing theoretical insights, following three phases, firstly by studying the origin and definitions of digital transformation and its different facets in order to better identify some amalgams between the different aspects of the digitalization process. The second phase is intended to put into perspective the international scale of the digital transformation of public services through a benchmark of the experience of some countries in terms of digital policy. While, the third phase will highlight the objective of the digital transformation of public sectors in the Moroccan context, focusing in particular on the state of the art of digital transformation in the public sector as well as the mapping of digitalization in the various public administrations.

1. Literature review:

Given the basic concepts and notions that interact in the phenomenon of digital transformation in general, it is necessary to try to clarify the terminology of some terms that arise from the digital field.

1.1 E-governance:

The definition and understanding of the concept of governance has undergone a historical evolution since its appearance at the 20th century. Governance was essentially introduced by the World Bank as a desirable requirement at the national level to enable and facilitate successful economic development reform (Haldenwang 2004) this concept that was adopted in the 1990s and has been expanded in a way that ensures a successful human development. Therefore, in order to comply with the requirements of international institutions for good governance, the agenda of public sector reform in developing countries has focused on institutional strengthening, with a twofold perspective:

- The reform of the structures associated with public administration;
- The development of personnel capable of operating and managing the organizational structures of the public administration in an effective way.

So, since globalization and the technological revolution have transformed public sector reform, capacity building must therefore be seen in strategic terms as a long-term action: an ongoing task to shape, redefine, and reorganize institutions with the help of evolving technologies and the refinement of human skills (UN 2003). This suggests that public sector reform and its process of "Capacity-building" incorporates new technologies as facilitating tools.

Heeks (Heeks 1999) explains this fact by noting that the reinvention of government is a continuation of new public management reforms. In this sense, globalization and the information age make public sector reform based on information technologies, taking part in IT to influence and facilitate good governance. Yet, a number of concepts related to IT have been increasingly used, including the notions of e-government, also often called e-government, and the model of government associated with it called e-governance (NU 2001).

It is therefore important to understand what factors influence users and potential users without their decisions to accept a new technology, and to actually use it. La literature reveals that the types of factors that can influence acceptance are varied. Par exemple, there are contextual, cultural and psychological, social (ethical or legal implications of using certain technologies) demographic (Romano, 1996), etc.

1.2. Government and E-Governance:

(Backus 2001) defines e-governance as the application of electronic means to facilitate and support interaction between government and citizens and between government and business on the one hand; and to update the internal functioning of government in order to streamline and deepen the democratic, governmental, and economic aspects of la governance on the other. E-governance consists of three elements according to Heeks (Heeks 2001):

- La E-administration: to improve government processes;
- The e-citizen and e-services: to connect citizens and serve them online;
- La e-society: to build interactions a within and across la civil society.

In this sense, e-governance offers two complementary aspects: political "focusing on la facilitation of democratic and participatory processes via citizen engagement" and technical "focusing on government operations and processes" (Bhatnagar 2004).

The question many organizations have is because some technologies in which they have invested heavily are not used effectively or are avoided by their target users. There are a good number of information systems, for example, that are never used or are abandoned soon after implementation. (Paulson, 2001). A number of authors point out that even if technologies show promise from a technical, utilitarian, or financial point of view, users (Bariey, 1986; Davis, 1986; Williams, 2005) do not always accept them.

The reasons then subtly appear and go beyond the framework of rational decisions traditionally advocated in the economic approach.

In recent years, in most developed countries, a number of initiatives have been taken regarding the implementation of e-government. Articles on the subject are multiplying, but the terminology used remains confusing and little. Not only does the notion of "administration", when it is electronic, not seem to refer only to the sphere of government itself, but the terms "e-government" or "cyber-government" are used in similar contexts. Given this lack of terminological clarity, it is important to ask what realities are covered by the concepts used; in particular, whether they are interchangeable and therefore included in the English notion of e-government, or whether they respond to distinct definitions¹. Consulting the Grand terminological dictionary² it does not show distinguished "Administration" from "e-government: the terms "electronic administration" "electronic government" and "e-government" are used interchangeably to refer to this concept. The word government is assigned a less extensive content than its usual content, taking the whole of government for la part administration. However, if these terms are not opposed, they complement each other. These notions are indeed part of "a process"³ whose ultimate stage would lead to the establishment of an online democracy.

They can also be grouped under the more encompassing notion of e-governance, a notion that refers to e-administration, but also to e-government or e-democracy⁴.

Thus, contrary to the English-speaking world where only the notion of "e-government" is used, the concepts of "administration" and "government" seem to have to be distinguished in French.

The Nomenclature of e-government The interaction between "government and government" (G2G), implies the sharing of data and the conduct of electronic exchanges between government actors. This involves both intra- and inter-institutional exchanges at the national level, as well as exchanges between the national, provincial and local levels. The interaction between "government and business" (G2B), encompasses business-specific transactions (e.g., payments made in the sale and achat of goods and

¹ Karim Benyekhlef " L'administration publique en ligne au Canada : précisions terminologiques et état de la réflexion " Ecole nationale d'administration | " Revue française d'administration publique " 2004/2 no110 | pages 267 à 277.

² The Grand dictionnaire terminologique de l'Office québécois de la langue française available at http://www.granddictionnaire.com/btml/fra/r_motclef/index1024_1.asp.

³ Secrétariat du Conseil du trésor, Modèle d'accompagnement des changements technologiques pour la fonction publique, fonction publique québécoise, 2001 : <http://www.tresor.gouv.qc.ca/resource/acrobat/projets/develop.pdf>.

⁴ Barsalo (René), Cartier (Michel) and Dumais (Michel), Réflexions, fiches d'actions et ressources pour stimuler la participation en matière de gouvernance participative (Reflections, action sheets and resources for stimulating participation in participatory governance), in Collaboration et communication numérique : la gouvernance participative (Collaboration and digital communication: participatory governance), Report for the City of Gatineau on participatory governance, Montreal, April 12.

services) as well as the online provision of business-oriented services. Government to Citizen (G2C) interaction encompasses initiatives to facilitate people's interaction with government as consumers of public services and as citizens. This includes interactions related to the delivery of public services, as well as participation in consultation and decision-making. **Source:** (UN 2003)

1.3. E-Administration and E-Governance: What is the distinction?

The "e-turn" adopted by current governments follows the logic of a three-step process. The first of these stages concerns the implementation of e-government; it aims to make administrative services accessible to citizens by facilitating procedures and increasing interactivity. This point on the efficiency of services is manifested through the circulation and sharing of information. We speak to personalization, the citizen is no longer perceived as a simple user but as a customer. Once the administration is put online, there is a need to rethink the mode of governance. This "new social contract" is referred to as "online government" or e-government. This "new" mode of governance implies a reform of traditional administrative institutions: state-centric administrative and political management is abandoned in favor of a model that is more adapted to "the needs of the citizen, the company and the members of the civil society".

II. The digitalization of public administration: a universal phenomenon, put into perspective at the international level and projected to the local context

This phase is devoted to proposing definitions of digital transformation in order to better define its concept, to study the different facets of the phenomenon by questioning its origin, its different modalities of implementation in the public and private sectors. As well as a brief projection on an international scale.

1.4. Definitions of digitization, digitalization, digital transformation, e-transformation:

All actors agree that digital transformation shifts value within sectors, whether industrial or service, whether companies operate with industrial customers or in the general public sector. The notion of business model, which had difficulty finding its place in the academic world at the end of the 1990s, has become one of the most studied concepts in management literature. At the same time, digital transformation is redrawing the place of the human being in companies. All tasks that can be automated are being automated, from the robotization of operations on automobile production lines to the automation of tasks of office workers or cashiers. Robotization also allows for on-demand production and the ability to customize products and services. "Gradually, the added value is shifting from the actual execution of tasks to three areas: the formulation of the customer's request, the design of the solution and the automata that execute them, and finally the service, which consists of delivering the customer." (Landier, 2014).

1.4.1. Definition of Digitization:

We often find that each article uses one or the other of these concepts to present this obvious fact, that organizations are accessing this profound renewal that is part and parcel of the digital economy that paces people's daily lives and creates economic value. Gartner defines digitalization as leveraging digital technologies to change business models and provide new revenue and value creation opportunities. The process of upgrading an enterprise to digital technologies is gradual and has in fact been going on for decades. This process is enabled by increasing interoperability, transparency of information across departmental and industry boundaries, automated assistance and support, and a trend toward decentralized decision making. According to Gartner⁵, the Internet of Things (IoT)⁶ is considered one of the main thrusts of digitalization (Cited in Firouzi et al., 2020). It refers to the use of new digital technologies, such as social media, mobile (...), to improve the customer experience, streamline operations or create new business models (Singh and Hess, 2017). For Vial (2019, p. 118),

1.4.2. Digital transformation:

Digital transformation refers to "a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes in its properties through combinations of information technology, computing, communication and connectivity." (Dörner and Edelman, 2015)⁷ published an article that presents digital as a way to hedge for a context in which companies and organizations operate. They believe that for some leaders, it is about technology. For others, digital is a new way to interact with customers. And for still others, it represents a whole new way of doing business. None of these definitions is necessarily wrong. However, these divergent perspectives permeate executive teams, as they reflect a lack of consistency and consensus vision on the company's strategic direction. This often results in incomplete initiatives or misdirected efforts that lead to missed opportunities or poor performance. The primary focus of this paper is e-government as a major trend in the digital transformation of the public sector. This transformation covers several public sector e-domains such as health, justice, education, etc., via dedicated electronic platforms (e-health, e-justice, e-learning, etc.).

2. The digitization of public administrations: a universal phenomenon

This is a strategic element in the development of administrative organizations in many countries. The United Nations notes in its 2018 annual survey on e-government (UN, 2018) that, since the early 2000s,

⁵ American advanced technology research and consulting firm

⁶ IBM defines IoT as the concept of connecting any device (physical object) to the Internet and other connected devices. It refers to the growing range of Internet-connected devices that capture or generate a huge amount of information on a daily basis.

⁷ For additional information, the McKinsey & Company portal <https://www.mckinsey.com> [accessed April 02, 2020].

e-government services have grown steadily around the world with the development of the Internet. UN studies thus suggest that the digitization of public administrations is increasingly a global phenomenon. To measure the level of e-government development, the UN has developed a specific index: the e-Government Development Index (EGDI). This index measures the evolution of the level of digitalization of the member states of the international organization. The EGDI is a composite index built on the basis of three other indices: the Telecommunications Infrastructure Index (TII), the Human Capital Index (HCI) and the Online Services Index (OSI). The Telecommunications Infrastructure Index measures the level of connectivity of the population. Five indicators make up the TII: the number of... The Human Capital Index measures the level of education and training of the population, The Human Capital Index is composed of four indicators: The Online Services Index assesses the level of use of digital tools in the delivery of public services by UN member states, The OSI is based on the results of a survey.

The EGDI makes it possible to situate the situation of states in terms of digitalization. It differentiates four classes of states that correspond to a level of e-government development each time higher. In 2018, Belgium is among the states with the highest level of e-government development, in line with other European countries. Among the forty states in this category, however, it is in the bottom third of the table, occupying the twenty-seventh position in 2018.

In terms of evolution, as shown in the graph below, e-government has followed a positive trend since the early 2000s, but remains below global and European indicators. Moreover, this evolution shows a rapid growth in the early 2000s, followed by a slowdown around 2008 and a continuous growth between 2008 and 2018 supported by a better internet accessibility of the population.

Graph 1: Evolution of the level of e-government development in Belgium

Source: UN - Calculations: IWEPS

2.1. The Case of France:

In 2014, France instituted a technology policy for the state that is based on three axes. The first axis that consists of aligning the information system of all public sector administrations and ensuring effective and efficient integrated data management. The second axis revolves around the establishment of a platform to create a dynamic in administrative data for the various actors. The third axis concerns e-administration, which serves to dematerialize the services rendered to the different actors. The European Commission in its Digital Transformation Scoreboard report (2018) has set up digital transformation framework conditions to position countries according to these indices.

Enabling factors:

- Digital infrastructure
- Investment and access to finance
- Supply and demand of digital skills
- E-leadership - Entrepreneurial culture Results:
- Integration of digital technology
- Changes in the ICT start-up environment

France's great strengths lie in its entrepreneurial culture, high investment, and access to finance (European Commission, 2018). Between 2016 and 2017, France improved significantly in terms of

entrepreneurial culture. Overall, France's profile seems relatively consistent in most dimensions, with the exception of its ICT environment of start-ups and digital transformation, where it lags behind other eurozone countries. Efforts have been made to integrate digital technologies into their production processes and to adapt business models accordingly (social media, etc.). In addition, France has a financial framework that encourages private companies to invest in information and communication technologies. French companies have easy access to financing on the stock markets and invest at high levels in R&D in digital technologies.

2.2. The pillars of the E-Society project au Morocco:

Digital transformation in Morocco: E.GOV - Digital Transformation of the administration A. Supporting the transformation of the administration and accelerating the execution of information technology projects. Modernization of the State's IT platforms a through the development of a global IT master plan and the strengthening of common ERPs, the interoperability of systems, and the use of shared data centers. / C. Reduction of the digital divide for the benefit of citizens (connectivity for all, primary, secondary and higher education programs, public access to WIFI) and businesses, especially SMEs (regions disadvantaged in connectivity). / D .Integrated transformation of critical sectors of the economy (PortNet, Santé,...) E / Regional digital HUB BPO strategic repositioning on Europe by encouraging value-added "Oriented Business models" and la setting up a promotional offer with specific incentives. F/ Digital Hub Africa Francophone with the development in particular of common infrastructure and physical networks and the encouragement of African talent to integrate Moroccan companies.

Digital Plan Morocco: A: Infrastructure DATACOM - the acceleration, in particular, of access to high and very high speed and generalization of access Data-mobile. B: Development of skills and training in information technology. C: Creation of an appropriate digital legal and regulatory framework a l'adaptation of public procurement of information technology services. D: Emergence of new national technology players. (E-Maroc 2020).

For the funding flight, financial resources to implement la measure of the programs as follows:

- A participation of private sector companies when they participate in public-private partenariats (PPP) or public-private business clusters (GIE). These models lend themselves well to financing telecommunications infrastructure, urban infrastructure for "Smart-cities" or Datacenter par exemple. The mechanism corresponds to capital expenditures granted partially by private operators in exchange for concessions remunerated over time.
- La mobilization of special funds, such as the Universal Telecommunications Service Fund (USF), or a other development funds such as the Hassan II Fund or the Social Cohesion Fund. These sources are well suited, for example, to financing initiatives with a digital equity vocation, reducing the la digital divide, supporting VSEs, etc...

- Concessional financing, part of which could be relocated to the IT component of the programs they fund. Example of the extension of the GID program, the digital component of la modernization of la justice, etc...
- The state budget, by reallocation of budget lines either between departments, or in favor of a redefinition of priorities, or via additional budget lines.
- Morocco a wanted to make e-government a national priority that will not only facilitate la life a to citizens but also la transparency of la management of la public administration towards la realization of an effective e-governance. Except that between la will and its execution on the ground, it leaves much to be desired. Proof is the latest figures of administration services unveiled par the Ministry in charge of la Reform of the Administration and la civil service (Rapport 2019) it emerges from the survey devoted to the assessment of la maturity of electronic services that the administration services of level to 4 completely dematerialized represent only 23.27%.
- La concretization of the electronic administration contributed, in the same way, to the improvement of the performances and the efficiency of the system of governance of the public sectors and will make it possible to extinguish the principal objectives posted in this direction to know:
 - The emergence of a modern, open and citizen administration;
 - The dematerialization of the relationship Administration - users and access to the labor market.

2.3. E-governance a Morocco: Some issues related to NICT:

Governments have placed Internet-led growth at the center of their concerns, and Morocco has ambitious plans to extend broadband Internet access to most of its population and a national information and communication technology (ICT) strategies, but many are still in the early stages of implementation.

In addition, there are bold initiatives and significant investments by la government and business. Demand is also being driven by government ICT strategies. Many organizations are putting in place processes. such as online benefit application, tax filing, and tax return applications, and efforts are focused on digitizing education, sovereignty, and public services. Ambitious ICT infrastructure is planned throughout the country, such as Maroc Telecom's \$1.2 million investment to upgrade its network and install fiber optics throughout Morocco. Submarine cable systems are being expanded and high-speed 4G networks are planned.

In addition, institutions are beginning to leverage the internet to reduce costs and increase performance. The industry is embracing online registration and la ticketing, for example, tends Banks are opting for online services and developing mobile microfinance products.

In relation to our research topic, Morocco has a diverse e-Governance profile. Through its e-government initiatives, it stands out for the relatively high proportion of its public spending, which represents (13%

of GDP), of which the trade balance is the main component of GDP (40%), thanks to exports from a growing industry.

The application of information and communication technologies (ICT) to all fields of economic, social and political life is growing steadily and influences the entire functioning of the society. ICTs can place the citizen and the company at the heart of administrative processes, they can create new channels of communication and an alternative mode of relations and offer, at a better cost, services more adequate to their expectations.

3. The state of play of digital transformation in Morocco:

In this section, we present the key elements of the state of play (digital initiatives and strategies launched in Morocco) and possible avenues for the digital transformation of public services in the Kingdom. Information and communication technologies (ICT) are an essential tool for socio-economic development. Digital transformation is one of the key trends in public and private organizations in the Kingdom today.

3.1. Digital initiatives and strategies launched by the Morocco:

In this respect, Morocco has embarked, like other countries, on a plan to restructure the information technology sector by promulgating in 1996 the law n°24-96 relating to the post and telecommunications, considered as the prelude to the first liberalization of the telecommunications sector. In this context, Morocco has adopted various digital strategies: the 1999-2003 five-year plan, e-Morocco 2010 covering the period 2005-2010, and the Digital Morocco 2013 strategy (MN2013) covering the period 2009-2013. The evaluation of online public services (Five-Year Plan 1999-2003, e-Morocco 2010 or MN2013) concerns the services provided by the public sector on the Internet, regardless of their degree of dematerialization. Moreover, the objective of these initiatives is to implement digitalized public services centered on the citizen/customer/user, seeking to strengthen the links between the latter and the public administration, through greater integration and widespread dissemination of information technologies at the level of all social actors (State, public administrations, companies and users).

As a brief reminder, the 1999-2003 five-year plan conceived and elaborated by the former SEPTTI, gave priority to the development of telecommunications and new technologies as a national priority for Morocco and a strategic choice to promote the economic, industrial and social development of the Kingdom. The main objectives of this five-year plan were based on the following points :

- Develop legislation that addresses the protection of commercial domain names, personal data and e-commerce issues;
- To initiate a decisive shift in education through the integration of computer and Internet tools in schools;
- Avoiding digital divides through policies that encourage the deployment of new technologies in the poorest regions and segments of the population;

- providing funds to encourage the creation of businesses in the era of the knowledge economy.
- The e-Morocco 2010 strategy aimed to develop the knowledge economy in Morocco and focus on a "dynamic and coordinated" public/private partnership based on two objectives. The strategy is based on four essential and closely related strategic objectives, namely reducing the digital divide and positioning Morocco at the international level, given its economic, cultural and geostrategic characteristics. As for the Digital Morocco 2013 strategy, it is based on four axes, namely
 - Access of citizens to broadband Internet and the promotion of communication and access to knowledge;
 - The improvement of public services through e-government programs to bring the administration closer to the needs of users in terms of efficiency, quality and transparency;
 - Encouraging SMEs to computerize their processes to increase their productivity;
 - The development of the IT industry⁸
 - What is important here is the evaluation of the implementation of e-services and their contribution to the improvement of public services, against the backdrop of bringing the administration closer to citizens/users.

3.2. Evaluation of strategies: Analysis by the Court of Auditors

In its report⁹ on the evaluation of the 2013 Digital Morocco strategy, the Court of Accounts pointed out that an analysis of the various digital plans that the Kingdom has had since 1999 revealed a certain weakening of efforts in terms of redeployment and implementation, expressed mainly by the instability of the government authority responsible for managing the ICT sector.

This has had a negative effect on the implementation, centralization of experiences related to the field in terms of implementation and traceability of the various documents related to the realization of projects. According to the same report, it should be noted that the evaluations of the various digital plans have been postponed sine die and that no update of the results and identification of weaknesses and factors hindering their implementation have been revealed. It should be noted that even before reaching the deadline set by the e-Morocco 2010 strategy that a new strategy has been launched. Thus, without rhyme or reason, there have been blatant breaks between the strategies around the same objectives.

The Court of Auditors, in the same evaluation report of the MN2013, highlights the poor progress of e-Government projects and the lack of commitment on the part of the State. The non-implementation of certain structuring projects such as the unique citizen identifier, the unique business identifier or the Gateway project, which consists of setting up an integrated interoperability platform at the level of the

⁸ the portal of the e-government program of the Kingdom of Morocco, report on the National Strategy for the Information Society and the Digital Economy <http://www.egov.ma/>.

⁹ the portal of the Court of Auditors, report on the evaluation of the "Maroc Numéric" 2013 strategy, Special report n° 05/13/CH IV <http://www.courdescomptes.ma/>.

e-Government program, which was part of the projects of the government's e-Morocco 2010 strategy entitled "One Gov". It was not until the royal speech of July 29, 2018 on the occasion of the 19th anniversary of the accession of the Sovereign to the Throne that the government could really concretize this Gateway project so that it is technically operational to rationally rethink the mode of delivery of administrative public services. The Sovereign specified in his speech that: "...and prevent, on the other hand, any public administration from requesting, on behalf of a potential investor, documents or information that are already in the possession of another public administration. It is indeed the responsibility of public services to organize a coordinated exchange of information, through the use of information technology and new technologies".

Achieving this goal requires the implementation of two pillars, the first is to share data between administrations and this by exchanging information for the outcome of a process requested by the citizen, and by creating federated databases for sharing and collaboration, giving public affairs managers access to credible, updated, and complete data on the citizen requesting the service or process in question.

The second axis consists of simplifying the management process by replacing the supporting documents requested by citizens by accessing a shared database or by communicating with the administration that is supposed to issue the supporting document that is the subject of the request via a secure "Gov to Gov" information exchange platform in order to verify the authenticity of the information provided by the user and that can be verified via the gateway. Basically, this is a key principle where the citizen has to provide his personal data only once, which implies a real mandatory sharing of data between different public sector administrations.

In another report entitled "Evaluation of online public services", the Court of Accounts carried out an analysis of Morocco's international positioning in terms of e-Government. It noted several findings. During the period 2010-2017, remarkable progress in terms of online services has been made in some administrations. such as taxes, customs and foreign trade, and land registry.

The assessment of the availability and online maturity of the main services is based on the European Commission's annual e-Government benchmarks. The assessment of the openness of public data is based on the use of raw data and the Open Data Barometer reports published by the World Wide Web Foundation. According to the same report, in terms of the development of online services, if Morocco has moved in the ranking of the United Nations (from 140th place in 2008 to 82nd place in 2014), this evolution has not lasted.

In 2018, Morocco has fallen heavily, ranking 78th in the e-Services Index and 110th in the e-Government Index. Therefore, in terms of the other two components of e-government, which are human capital and IT infrastructure, Morocco's level has not seen any real change, it is maintained at a low level internationally: the Kingdom is positioned at 104th place in terms of IT infrastructure and 148th

place in terms of human capital. This represents an obstacle to the widespread use of online services developed by the public domain.

Graph 2: Evolution of Morocco's ranking on the "Online Services", "Human Capital" and "IT Infrastructure" indices

Conclusion:

In Morocco, we can see that the state has launched several projects to digitalize public administrations. If the Kingdom is late in the field of digitization of its public sector, it has serious advantages to show. With the health crisis that the world is currently experiencing (Covid-19), the digitization of the public sector becomes more than ever a necessity of the first order, in order to alleviate certain procedures and improve the access of citizens/users to public services (Santiso and Bernard, 2019), through the management of data in an efficient and effective manner and the dematerialization of administrative procedures, and to build a digitalized administration that favors a new generation of IT...

The organizational culture of each country, i.e., the digitization process must be adapted to the public sector context to identify the strategic axes and challenges and allocate high value-added technologies for an integrated and successful mapping of digitization. High value-added technologies for an integrated and successful digitalization mapping. In this regard, the call for the implementation of New Public Management practices is essential to foster digital transformation in public organizations.

It is important to emphasize that the well-being of citizens is one of the criteria for evaluating public action (Offredi and Laffut, 2013), and this remains valid for the digitalization policy of public administrations. The question that arises at this level is to identify the ways in which digital transformation influences the improvement of the quality of service and the increase in the sense of citizenship of individuals.

Of course, it is not a matter of "throwing the baby out with the bathwater", as IT applications are indeed the support of often positive transformations. The choice is not between blissful acceptance and unconditional rejection of ICTs, but rather to adopt a critical analysis posture that allows us to disentangle the tensions, paradoxes or contradictions that can be observed in the very field of public action.

In other words, it is a matter of being wary of false evidence (Marx, 2003), of remembering that there is no such thing as a truly free lunch, otherwise the risk is that "the more things change, the more they are the same... in a much more complicated way than before".

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